

Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp and Aflatoxins in luncheon, minced meat and sausage

Mahmoud E. Elsayed¹; Abdelazeem M. Algammal¹; Eman M. El-Diasty², Reham R. Abouelmaatti³ and Sarah M. Abbas⁴

¹Department of Bacteriology, Immunology and Mycology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, 41522, Egypt.

²Animal Health Research Institute, Agriculture Research center, El-Dokki Giza, Egypt.

³Key Laboratory of Animal Epidemiology and Zoonosis, Sharika Veterinary Directorate, General Authority for Veterinary Services, Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt

⁴Animal Health Research Institute, Port Said branch, Agriculture Research center, El-Dokki Giza, Egypt.

Abstract

Meat is considered the main source of animal protein worldwide. To investigate the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in luncheon, minced meat and sausage as well as detection of Aflatoxins, a total of 105 samples of luncheon, minced meat and sausage (35 of each) were randomly collected from different markets in Port Said governorate, Egypt. The collected specimens were subjected to mycological examination, where the mean mould count was $1.3 \times 10^2 \pm 2.1 \times 10$ cfu/g; $2.8 \times 10^2 \pm 4.3 \times 10$ cfu /g and $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ cfu/g in luncheon, minced meat and sausage, respectively. The prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in luncheon, minced meat and sausage was (25.71%), (48.57%) and (77.1%), respectively. *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from luncheon, minced meat and sausage with prevalence (25.71%), (34.28%) and (25.71%), respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in minced meat and sausage was (14.28%) and (31.42%), respectively. Qualitative and quantitative estimation of Aflatoxins was carried out on the collected samples and the isolated *A. flavus* strains, where Aflatoxin B₁ could be detected in 3 samples of luncheon constituting (8.57%) with minimum detection level 8µg/ kg, while the Aflatoxin G₁, could be found in one luncheon sample (2.9%) with minimum detection 4µg/ kg. In conclusion, *A. flavus* and *A. niger* were the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from meat products. *A. flavus* is considered the main cause of meat products spoilage, leading to severe economic losses and comprises a public health problem due to the production of Aflatoxins so, rigorous hygienic procedures must be applied during the manufacturing process.

Keywords: *Aspergillus*, Aflatoxin, luncheon, minced meat, sausage.

Introduction

Fungi are considered a major group of microorganisms, which are widely distributed in nature and cause spoilage of meat and its products globally. The occurrence of fungal growth in meat products indicates the production of mycotoxins resulting in public health problems. Genera such as *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* spp are the most predominant microorganisms incriminated in meat and meat products spoilage (Toldra, 2009 and Abouelmaatti et al 2013). The main predisposing factors that favor the growth of microorganisms in meat and meat

products are the presence of moisture, the temperature of storage and oxygen accessibility. These factors together with the high nutritive value of meat products encourage the microbial growth leading to food spoilage (Frazier and Westhoff, 2004 and Algammal and Elfeil 2015). The microbial contamination is the main problem in the process of food production, especially of animal origin. Meat and its products can be contaminated with various fungi during processing and packaging. These Fungi transmitted to the meat products from the surrounding environment, tools, and workers during

the manufacturing process (Sachindra *et al.*, 2005 and Elfeil *et al* 2012). Moulds are ubiquitous microorganisms and widely distributed in nature, so can easily gain access to the various meat products through contaminated processing equipment or dust, resulting in illness and allergic symptoms (Stagnitta *et al.*, 2006, Elfeil *et al* 2016 and Enany *et al* 2018). Aflatoxin B₁ is considered one the major hepatocarcinogenic agents and could assess hazards to man (Maktabi *et al.*, 2016, Sedeik *et al* 2018 and Elhady *et al* 2018). The continuous exposure to aflatoxin over the international guideline (twenty ppb) could influence various organs; the main affected organ is liver. Aflatoxins cause hepatotoxicity in both animals and man. Food- Aflatoxicosis could occur in acute to chronic forms, and the severity of the disease could be ranged from mild to severe illness, including hepatic and may be incriminated in liver cancer. (FDA, 2013 and Eid *et al* 2016). This work was planned to investigate the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in luncheon, minced meat and sausage as well as detection of Aflatoxins.

Material and methods

Sampling

A total of 105 random samples of Luncheon, minced meat and sausage (35 of each) were collected from different markets in Port Said governorate, Egypt. The collected samples were kept in sterile polyethylene bags and preserved in an ice box then transferred to the laboratory as soon as possible under complete aseptic condition for the mycological examination.

Sample preparation

The collected samples were prepared according to the methods described by

(APHA, 2001). Twenty-five grams from each sample were carefully and aseptically homogenized in a blender with 225 ml of sterile peptone water 0.1% to form a dilution of 1:10, from which tenth fold serial dilutions were accomplished up to 10⁶.

Determination of total mould count (ISO, 2008)

One ml of the previously prepared serial dilution was separately poured into duplicated Petri dishes carefully and mixed with Dichloran Rose Bengal Chloramphenicol (DRBC) agar, incubated at 25⁰C for 5-7 days. The incubated plates were examined for mould growth and then transferred onto Sabouraud's dextrose slope agar to be incubated at room temperature for 5 days and kept for further identification. The mould counted /gm was separately calculated and recorded.

Identification of *Aspergillus* spp (Pitt and Hocking, 2009)

a. Macroscopical examination

The macroscopical examination of mould colonies included the rate and pattern of growth, as color, texture, basal and surface mycelia, reverse of colony and the rate of colony growth and diameter. The examination was carried out by using a magnifying hand lens.

b. Microscopical examination

From the periphery of 5-7 days old colony, a triangular piece was transferred to a clean glass slide, with 2 mycological needles, the piece of the colony was distributed with one to two drops of lactophenol stain and then covered by a clean cover slip, followed by gentle pressure to remove the excess of fluid and air bubbles as well as to depress the hyphae and other structures for facilitating microscopic examination. The prepared slides were examined under low power

and oil immersion lenses to characterize the morphological structures of the mould growth concerning the conidial stage, head, vesicle, strigmata, conidiophore, and conidia. Also, the Hulle cells or other hyphal peculiarities, Sclerotia and ascosporic stage were observed and recorded.

Extraction of Aflatoxin B₁ and Aflatoxin G₁ residues in luncheon, minced meat and sausage

Mycotoxins were extracted from the collected luncheon and minced meat specimens according to the methods described by (Stubblefield *et al.*, 1982). Thin layer chromatography was carried out for detection of mycotoxins as described by (Howell and Taylor, 1981). Plates were visualized under short and long UV light.

Screening of the isolated *A. flavus* strains for production of Aflatoxins (Davis *et al.*, 1966):

Cultivation of *A. flavus* and extraction of Aflatoxins:

The isolated strains of *A. flavus* were inoculated onto 50 ml of yeast extract solution containing 15 % sucrose. The inoculated flasks were incubated at 25°C for 21 days. At the end of incubation period, 25 ml of chloroform were added, and the mixture was thoroughly mixed for one minute in ultralux apparatus. The mixture was then centrifuged (3000 rpm) for 10 minutes where the chloroform layer was decanted, the chloroform extraction was repeated only once. One ml ethanol, 3gm copper-(111)-hydroxide, carbonate and from 5-10gm anhydrous sodium sulphate were added to the chloroform extract, mixed well and filtrated. The filtrate was then evaporated by warming on boiling water bath until dryness. The

residue was cooled and resuspended in exactly 5 ml of chloroform.

Qualitative and Quantitative Estimation of Aflatoxins:

Chromatographic plates were examined for qualitative estimation of Aflatoxins. Colors and intensities of the unknown spots were compared with those of the standard reference Aflatoxin B₁ (Sigma, USA). Samples extracts which were found to contain mycotoxins by the qualitative technique were further estimated quantitatively according to (Schullerand and van, 1981). The mycotoxins concentration in the sample extracts determined by matching the fluorescence intensities of the toxin spots in the sample with those of the standard.

Results

Total mould count

In the present work, the mean mould count was $1.3 \times 10^2 \pm 2.1 \times 10$ cfu /g; $2.8 \times 10^2 \pm 4.3 \times 10$ cfu /g. and $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ cfu/g in luncheon, minced meat and sausage, respectively as illustrated in Table (1).

Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in examined luncheon and minced meat and sausage

As described in Table (2), the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in luncheon, minced meat and sausage was (25.71%), (48.57%) and (77.1%) respectively. *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from luncheon, minced meat and sausage with prevalence (25.71%), (34.28%) and (25.71%), respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in minced meat and sausage was (14.28%) and (31.42%) respectively. Furthermore, other *Aspergillus* spp were isolated from the examined sausage samples including; *A. ochraceus* (14.28%), *A. terreus* (8.57 %) and *A. niveus* (5.71%).

Estimation of Aflatoxins in the examined samples and the isolated *A. flavus* strains

In the present study, Aflatoxin B₁ could be detected in 3 samples of luncheon constituting (8.57%). The minimum detected level of Aflatoxin B₁ in luncheon samples was 8µg/ kg, while maximum level was 10.3µg/kg with a mean value of 10.9 ±1.9µg/kg. Concerning the Aflatoxin G₁, it could be found in one only in luncheon samples (2.9%), the minimum detected level of Aflatoxin G₁ was 4µg/ kg. Three *A. flavus* strains originated from

luncheon samples and 4 strains originated from sausage samples were positive for Aflatoxin B₁ with a mean value of 19.77 (±10.3) mg/L and 16.8 (±2.43) mg/L, respectively. All the isolated *A. flavus* strains from minced meat were negative for Aflatoxin B₁. Concerning Aflatoxin G₁, two *A. flavus* strains originated from luncheon samples, one strain originated from sausage samples and 8 strains originated from minced meat samples were positive for aflatoxin G₁ with a mean value of 30.5±4.88mg/L.

Table (1): Total mould counts cfu/g in examined luncheon, minced meat and sausage samples

Meat products	Total mould count (cfu/g)		
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean(±SE)
Luncheon	1x10	3.5x10 ²	1.3x10 ² ±2.1x10
Minced meat	1x10	8.8x10 ²	2.8x10 ² ±4.3x10
Sausage	9x10	3.4x10 ⁴	6.9x10 ² ±1.2x10 ²

Table (2): Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in examined luncheon, minced meat and sausage samples

<i>Aspergillus</i> species	Luncheon n=35		Minced meat n=35		Sausage n=35	
	No of +ve samples	%	No of +ve samples	%	No of +ve samples	%
<i>A. flavus</i>	9	25.71	12	34.28	9	25.71
<i>A. niger</i>	-	-	5	14.28	11	31.42
<i>A. niveus</i> + <i>A. terreus</i>	-	-	-	-	2	5.71/ each
<i>A. ochraceus</i>	-	-	-	-	4	11.4
<i>A. terreus</i> + <i>A. ochraceus</i>	-	-	-	-	1	2.8 / each
Total	9	25.71	17	48.57	27	77.1

Table (3): Estimation of Aflatoxins in the examined samples and the isolated *A. flavus* strains

Meat products	No of samples	+ve samples for Aflatoxin B ₁		+ve samples for Aflatoxin G ₁		No of <i>A. flavus</i>	+ ve strains for Aflatoxin B ₁		+ ve strains for Aflatoxin G ₁	
		No	%	No	%		No	%	No	%
		Luncheon	35	3	8.57		1	2.9	9	3
Sausage	35	-	-	-	-	9	2	22.2	1	11.1
Minced meat	35	-	-	-	-	12	-	-	8	66.6

Discussion

Meat is preferred by millions of people all over the world as a major source of animal protein. But, meat is considered a favorable media for growth of various pathogens, so could be spoiled rapidly. The decomposition of different

constituents of meat including protein and fat resulting in bad odors and other unfavorable changes. Therefore, spoilage of meat and meat products should be limited and controlled to protect the human consumers from infection and allergy (Aksoy *et al.*, 2014). In the present

study, the mean mould count was $1.3 \times 10^2 \pm 2.1 \times 10$ cfu/g; $2.8 \times 10^2 \pm 4.3 \times 10$ cfu/g. and $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ in luncheon, minced meat and sausage, respectively as described in Table (1). The results of luncheon samples nearly similar to those obtained by (Ouf *et al.*, 2010) who reported that the mean mould count was $1.6 \times 10^2 \pm 29.6$ cfu/g and (Morshdy *et al.*, 2009) who found that the mean total mould count of luncheon samples was $1.7 \times 10^2 \pm 0.54 \times 10^2$ cfu/g, while higher prevalence was recorded by (Ali *et al.*, 2005) as $3.1 \times 10^3 \pm 0.3 \times 10^3$ cfu/g. The results of the examined minced meat samples are nearly similar to those obtained by (Khalifa, 2015) and (Abu Zaid, 2015), and are lower than those obtained by (Saleh and Salah El-Dien, 2006) and (Eleiwa and El-Diasty, 2014) who reported that total mould counts in examined minced meat samples was 3.0×10^3 . Minced beef may be contaminated during production, processing, storage and marketing with biological agents that may be harmful to human health. The results of the mean of total mould count of sausage in this work are nearly similar to (fatema, 2016) who reported that the mean value was $8.7 \times 10^2 \pm 4.4 \times 10^2$ (cfu/g). Sausage is exposed to elevated degrees of temperature during the processing. But this temperature is not effective to kill all the present pathogens. (Özdemir, 1997). In the present work, the prevalence of *Aspergillus spp* in luncheon, minced meat and sausage was (25.71%), (48.57%) and (77.1%) respectively, (Table 2). *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus spp* isolated from luncheon, minced meat and sausage with prevalence (25.71%), (34.28%) and (25.71%) respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in minced meat and sausage was

(14.28%) and (31.42%) respectively. Furthermore, other *Aspergillus spp* were isolated from the examined sausage samples including; *A. ochraceus* (14.28%), *A. terreus* (8.57 %) and *A. niveus* (5.71%). The obtained results are nearly similar to those reported by (Ismail *et al.*, 2013; Eleiwa and El-Diasty, 2014; Morshdy *et al.*, 2015 and Abo El yazeed *et al.*, 2015) who determined that *Aspergillus* species were the most predominant mould species isolated from meat products samples. In the present work, the most prevalent species were *A. flavus* followed by *A. niger* which agreed with (Ebraheem and Mohamed, 2012) who found that the predominant species of *Aspergillus* in luncheon were *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. oryzae*, and *A. niger*. (Shaltout and Salem, 2000) isolated *Aspergillus* species including; *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, *A. ochraceus*, and *A. terreus* from minced meat, while (Brr *et al.*, 2004) reported that *A. flavus* and *A. niger* as the most prevalent strains from meat products. In the present study, as described in Table (3) Aflatoxin B₁ could be detected in 3 samples of luncheon constituting (8.57%), while the Aflatoxin G₁ could be found in one only in luncheon samples (2.9%). Three *A. flavus* strains originated from luncheon samples and 4 strains originated from sausage samples were positive for Aflatoxin B₁, while all the isolated *A. flavus* strains from minced meat were negative for Aflatoxin B₁. Concerning Aflatoxin G₁, two *A. flavus* strains originated from luncheon samples, one strain originated from sausage samples and 8 strains originated from minced meat samples were positive for aflatoxin G₁. These results are similar to those obtained by reported by (Shaltout *et al.*, 2014) and

(Ismail *et al.*, 2013). Aflatoxins could be produced by moulds in meat and meat products under natural conditions resulting in public health problems (Tavcar-Kalcher *et al.*, 2007).

In conclusion, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger* were the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from meat products. *Aspergillus flavus* is considered the main cause of meat products spoilage, leading to severe economic losses and comprises a public health problem due to the production of Aflatoxins so, rigorous hygienic procedures must be applied during the manufacturing process. Aflatoxin B₁ is the main Aflatoxin occurred in luncheon and sausage followed by Aflatoxin G₁,

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